

Use of Serious Games for Motor and Cognitive Development in Youths with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Systematic Review

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Abstract— Given the increasing exposure of children to digital technologies and the demonstrated effectiveness of serious games (SGs) in educational and therapeutic settings, there has been growing interest in their application for fostering motor and cognitive skills in neurodivergent youth, particularly those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). In this context, the present study conducted a literature review analysing research published in internationally recognised databases. By offering a critical and comprehensive review of the existing literature, this research seeks to highlight the potential of SGs as a complementary resource in clinical interventions. Following the screening process, eight articles were included. While traditional therapeutic methods remain irreplaceable, the findings suggest that SGs serve as a valuable complementary approach, offering significant and promising contributions in this field.

Keywords — *serious games, Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), assistive technology and therapeutic intervention*

I. INTRODUCTION

Serious games (SGs) represent a category of electronic games developed with purposes that go beyond mere entertainment, as they aim to foster the development, enhancement, and learning of specific skills. In this regard, within the fields of health and education, these games have been widely used as supportive tools in therapeutic and pedagogical interventions. Unlike traditional games, SGs are specifically designed to promote user engagement while simultaneously contributing to the strengthening of cognitive, motor, and social skills [1] [2].

Currently, the relevance of SGs has grown significantly, particularly due to the exponential increase in children's use of digital technologies. As a result, the easy access to devices such as smartphones, tablets, and computers has made interaction with digital applications a routine part of childhood. Consequently, this scenario has driven research focused on the application of digital games as complementary resources in the treatment of various medical conditions and neurodevelopmental disorders [3] [4].

Among the various neurodevelopmental conditions, Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is particularly notable due to its complex and diverse behavioural manifestations. A common yet often underestimated aspect of ASD involves motor difficulties. Despite their high prevalence, these challenges are frequently overlooked in clinical settings. Impairments in locomotion, postural control, and manual dexterity can significantly hinder children's ability to perform self-care tasks and engage in play—key activities for healthy development. This, in turn, may lead to a cycle of physical inactivity and social exclusion [5].

Beyond motor issues, ASD also has a profound impact on cognitive functioning, often affecting communication, social interaction, and the execution of daily routines. Many children with ASD display a heterogeneous cognitive profile—excelling in certain areas while struggling with others, such as logical reasoning and information processing. Given this complexity, fostering the integrated development of motor and cognitive skills is essential for promoting autonomy and enhancing social inclusion [6] [7].

In this context, the present study aims to explore the use of SGs as supportive tools for the development of motor and cognitive abilities in children with ASD. By offering a critical and comprehensive review of the existing literature, this research seeks to highlight the potential of SGs as a complementary resource in clinical interventions, ultimately contributing to greater inclusion and improved quality of life for these children.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The first step in conducting this systematic review was to formulate a clear and focused research question. To guide this process, the PICO framework was used, in which each component represents a critical element of the research question: P (Population), I (Intervention), C (Comparison), and O (Outcome). Based on this model, the central research question established was: "Are serious Games more effective than traditional therapies for improving motor and cognitive skills in young individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder?"

Based on this question, essential keywords were selected to guide the literature search: serious games, ASD, motor and cognitive skills, and traditional therapies. The search strategy utilised the following Boolean search string: "serious games" AND ("motor skills" OR "cognitive skills") AND (autism OR "autism spectrum disorder" OR ASD) AND ("conventional therapy" OR "traditional therapy" OR therapy) NOT adults. Searches were performed in both English and Portuguese using the following databases: PubMed, Google Scholar, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and Scopus.

The literature search was conducted between February and April 2025, with a publication date filter restricting results to the past five years to ensure inclusion of recent and relevant studies. After collecting and organising the retrieved articles, the screening process began, applying two exclusion criteria:

- Incomplete or inaccessible articles;
- Publications that diverge from the topic.

The PRISMA tool was used for the identification, selection, eligibility, and inclusion of articles. It provides preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses. Additionally, the Rayyan web application was employed. By importing Research Information Systems (.ris) files, which contain bibliographic data of the publications found in the searches across the selected databases, this software displays information from different sources in an integrated interface, facilitating the processes of selection, eligibility, and inclusion in the systematic review [8].

Assessing the quality of the studies included in the systematic review is also a fundamental aspect. For this purpose, specific criteria were adopted [9], based on a set of evaluative questions, with scoring assigned as follows: 1 point for "Yes", 0.5 points for "Partially", and 0 points for "No".

- Is the article based on research (or only expert opinion)?
- Is there a clear statement of the research objectives?
- Was there a control group to compare the results?
- Were data collected to address the research question?
- Is there a clear statement of the results?
- Can the findings of the study be applied in clinical practice?

III. RESULTS

This section is organised into three subsections. The first details the article selection and screening process carried out for this review. The second presents the findings of the included studies, and the third offers a qualitative evaluation of their methodological quality.

A. Study Selection Process

The initial database search yielded 184 publications. After removing 30 duplicates, 154 unique records remained. A preliminary screening excluded 144 articles that did not align with the review's focus, narrowing the pool to 10 potentially relevant studies. These articles then underwent an eligibility assessment based on two key criteria: (1) whether the study described the characteristics of the SGs used, and (2) whether full access to the article was available free of charge. Based on these criteria, 8 studies met the inclusion requirements and were incorporated into this systematic review. Figure 1 shows the PRISMA flowchart for this research.

Fig. 1. PRISMA - Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis

B. Description of Study Results

In the study by Freitas et al. [10], a set of serious cognitive games was thoughtfully developed and validated. These games were created using Unity 3D and seamlessly integrated with the MARIA T21 assistive robot, which employs sensors and cameras to dynamically adjust the difficulty of the game in real time (dynamic difficulty adjustment - DDA) during Applied Behaviour Analysis Therapy Sessions (ABA) with children diagnosed with ASD. Together, three innovative games were designed, each offering unique interactive experiences, as summarised below:

- **Memô:** This memory-based game challenges the child to replicate increasingly complex sequences of colored squares that light up and produce sounds. To support the player, the MARIA T21 robot steps in with helpful hints and voice commands whenever mistakes are made, helping to refocus attention. The game meticulously tracks key metrics such as session duration, number of robot assists, and user score, providing valuable feedback.

- **Globin Gold:** In this action-packed game, the child must defend a treasure chest from a host of approaching enemies or monsters. By visually focusing on an enemy, the child slows its advance, and maintaining this gaze for a set period eliminates the threat, encouraging sustained attention and engagement.
- **MARIA's Homework:** This educational game invites the child to answer questions spanning six thematic categories, covering diverse topics vital for academic and social development. At the end of each session, the game delivers personalised feedback, reinforcing learning and progress.

Eighteen children diagnosed with ASD, aged between 5 and 9 years, participated in this research and received support from occupational therapists. The games were implemented across different weeks. *Memô* was utilised throughout 8 weeks of the study, with the first four weeks played without dynamic difficulty adjustment (DDA) and the last four weeks with DDA enabled. *Globin Gold* was applied for six weeks, while *MARIA's Homework* was used for four weeks with only 8 participants, featuring questions tailored to each child's individual difficulty level. The authors concluded that dynamic difficulty adjustment effectively maintained user engagement and customised challenges to match individual capabilities. Furthermore, they found that combining SGs with assistive robotic technologies offers a promising and personalised approach to support the development of children with ASD, enhancing the effectiveness of ABA-based therapy.

In the study conducted by Atika et al. [11], a serious game titled *Eggy's Diary* was introduced, based on social stories for children also diagnosed with ASD. *Eggy's Diary* was designed and programmed using the *Unity 3D* platform exclusively for Android devices. The game integrates elements of social stories and the precoding methodology, aiming to enhance cognitive, motor, and communication skills in these children. Each level features a typical daily routine activity—for example, washing or dressing—that the player must organise into the correct sequence using instructions provided through images, texts, or voice commands on the interface. The mechanics and design of this serious game emphasise visual simplicity, effective use of colour, and clear commands, while carefully following established guidelines tailored for children with ASD. During the test, five children between the ages of 5 and 12 years evaluated the usability of the game, with scores indicating ease of learning (61.35%), memorisation (62%), efficiency (72%) and satisfaction (75%). According to the authors, despite the small sample size, the game captured the interest and participation of the participants as they worked to solve the challenges. In addition, they suggest that this game has potential as a complementary tool for therapeutic interventions targeting children with ASD.

Alvari et al. [12] investigated the application and outcomes of a serious game involving children and adolescents diagnosed with ASD. By combining biosensor data with therapist observations, the study was able to correlate physiological indicators such as heart rate and respiratory rate with participant engagement and behaviour.

The game comprised three immersive Virtual Reality stages: (1) the Coin Search Scenario, where players searched for coins in a virtual park; (2) the Station Scenario, in which collected coins were used to purchase tickets for travel to a planet to collect essential materials; and (3) the Battle Scenario, where players shot rocks to find those materials. This diverse range of VR environments effectively enhanced participant engagement and provided opportunities to develop social skills, decision-making, and emotional regulation. Notably, physiological responses varied throughout the stages, reflecting different levels of arousal and involvement between child and adolescent participants. Additionally, therapists observed behavioural improvements throughout the sessions, highlighting Virtual Reality's potential as a therapeutic tool for fostering socioemotional development in children and adolescents with ASD.

Reyes et al. [13] presented another serious game, *"Aprendiendo con TEA"*. Developed in Spanish using the *Unity* platform, this application is accessible across multiple devices. Targeting children aged 5 to 12 with ASD, the game integrates established therapeutic strategies, including Applied Behaviour Analysis and theory of mind exercises. Activities encompass emotion recognition, memory, attention, and interactive storytelling, all with adjustable difficulty levels tailored to individual needs. Therapist feedback collected through surveys indicated broad approval of the game as a complementary tool to traditional therapies, particularly for enhancing socioemotional and cognitive skills. The application has garnered over 500 downloads, with significant uptake in Spain, Argentina, and Mexico, underscoring its potential as an accessible and effective resource for supporting children with ASD.

In a study by Minissi et al. [14], two SGs developed in virtual reality were evaluated for their effectiveness in promoting motor learning among children with ASD. The sample comprised 40 children, including 20 diagnosed with ASD and 20 with typical development, aged between 3 and 7 years. The study hypothesised that children with ASD would initially perform at lower levels compared to their typically developing peers but that both groups would show measurable improvements in motor skills through repeated gameplay. Each participant completed two sessions per game, allowing the researchers to analyse motor learning progress across successive attempts.

- **Bubble Task (BT):** In this game, the participant had to pop thirty bubbles that fell in pairs, each with different colours and progressively increasing speed every 10 bubbles. The task required the use of the upper limbs and involved oculomotor coordination with a high degree of freedom of movement.
- **Flower Task (FT):** In this task, the user had to pick up a flower located on the left side of the virtual environment and carry it to the opposite side. This activity demanded precision, a lower degree of freedom in arm movement, and also involved oculomotor coordination. The time limit to complete the task was 300 seconds to move five flowers.

The results revealed distinct performance patterns across

tasks. In the **Bubble Task (BT)**, children with ASD exhibited longer response times and lower accuracy compared to their typically developing (TD) peers, with no significant evidence of motor learning through repeated attempts. Conversely, the **Flower Task (FT)** showed promising signs of motor learning in children with ASD, who notably reduced their completion times on the second try, while the TD group’s performance remained stable. These findings suggest that despite initial challenges, children with ASD are capable of developing motor adaptations over time. The authors emphasise that SGs delivered through virtual reality hold great potential to facilitate implicit motor skill acquisition in this population.

In a separate study, Shohieb, Doenyas, and Elhady [15] engaged seven children with ASD, aged 5 to 10 years, in an educational game called *Pickstar*. Designed to teach Arabic vocabulary through interactive word-image associations, the game incorporated playful mechanics such as falling stars and auditory reinforcements—including animal sounds, applause, and word pronunciations—to enhance learning. Over four weeks, the children engaged with the game for 10 to 15 minutes each day. A standout feature was the Dynamic Difficulty Adjustment (DDA) system, which tailored the game’s challenge in real-time to maintain an optimal success rate of 70%, thereby preventing frustration and encouraging motivation. *Pickstar* demonstrated high usability and satisfaction among both children and caregivers, significantly boosting vocabulary acquisition, engagement, and learner autonomy, while also easing caregiver responsibilities. Pre- and post-intervention interviews with parents and caregivers further highlighted increased participation and enthusiasm among the children, underscoring the game’s effectiveness as a home-based educational tool.

Jamey et al. [16] explored the use of *Rhythm Workers*—a rhythm-based serious game previously validated for dyslexia treatment—for motor and cognitive rehabilitation in youth with ASD. The study included 32 children aged 7 to 12 across Canada. Provided with tablets and headphones, participants played for 30 minutes a day, five days a week, over two weeks, totalling 300 minutes of gameplay. Mood, perceived progress, difficulty, and engagement were systematically tracked through questionnaires administered before and after each session, with the latter two assessed via a 5-point Likert scale. The findings supported the game’s utility, demonstrating significant improvements in sensorimotor synchronisation and functional abilities, highlighting the promise of rhythm-based interventions for this population.

Lastly, El-Sattar et al. [17] introduced an innovative participatory research system designed to enhance learning in children with ASD, centred around the pedagogical framework behind the game TASALY. The SALY system architecture enables therapists to define game difficulty, mechanics, and educational elements, with the game dynamically adjusting its challenge level based on the player’s performance after each session. This feedback loop continues iteratively, ensuring the game’s progression matches the user’s needs. Thirty-three children with ASD, aged 7 to 15, engaged with TASALY once weekly over seven weeks, in sessions lasting ninety minutes. Usability tests conducted before and after the intervention indicated increased therapeutic engagement, as well as improved

emotional recognition and expression. This study illustrates the powerful potential of adaptive, therapist-guided SGs in fostering socioemotional development in children with ASD.

C. Qualitative Assessment

The qualitative assessment of the studies included in the systematic review was conducted based on six main criteria: nature of the research (A), clarity of objectives (B), presence of a control group (C), data collection addressing the research question (D), clarity of results (E), and clinical applicability (F). As shown in Table 1, the studies received total scores ranging from 4.5 to 6 points.

TABLE 1. Qualitative Assessment Items

Study	A	B	C	D	E	F	Total
[10]	1	1	0	1	1	1	5
[11]	1	1	0	1	1	0,5	4,5
[12]	1	1	0	1	1	0,5	4,5
[13]	1	1	0	1	1	1	5
[14]	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	5,5
[15]	1	1	0	1	1	0,5	4,5
[16]	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
[17]	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
Total	8	8	3	8	8	6	

It is observed that all studies received the maximum score (1 point) on criteria A (nature of the research), B (clarity of objectives), D (data collection), and E (clarity of results), demonstrating methodological quality in study design and presentation of findings. Conversely, criterion C (presence of control group) received the lowest total score (3 points across all studies), indicating that only three studies included comparisons with control groups. This limits the ability to establish strong causal relationships between the use of SGs and the observed outcomes. Criterion F (clinical applicability) also varied, with three studies receiving partial scores (0.5 points).

IV. DISCUSSION

Overall, the qualitative assessment results demonstrate that most studies maintain methodological consistency, although some specific gaps remain. This evaluation shows that, in general, the studies included in this review possessed good methodological quality. However, the fact that only two studies achieved the maximum score of 6—without losing points due to the absence of control groups or challenges in clinical application—highlights the intrinsic diversity of studies within this research field. Many articles focus on the application of a single serious game and evaluate its outcomes in isolation, making broad generalisations of the findings difficult and limiting direct comparison between different interventions.

The findings of this review indicate that SGs are promising tools to support the motor and cognitive development of children with ASD. Several included studies reported improvements in attention, motor task execution,

and social interaction, especially when SGs were combined with other technologies such as virtual reality or assistive robotics. However there are still limitations in applicability of these technologies in the context of reproducibility, commercialization [18]. Although limitations for simulating other sensory stimuli such as tactile, olfactory and oral input pointed by previous studies [19] have been gradually being overcome by new solutions, specially in mobile applications [16] [11].

Nonetheless, direct comparisons between studies remain difficult due to considerable methodological heterogeneity. Most studies investigate the effects of a specific serious game as a complementary therapy but do not comprehensively evaluate SGs as a therapeutic strategy overall. They tend to provide isolated analyses without systematic comparisons to traditional approaches.

Despite their exploratory nature and methodological limitations, the results consistently point to improvements in patients treated with SGs. Thus, while traditional therapies cannot be replaced, the evidence suggests that SGs represent a promising complementary alternative in therapeutic contexts. Moreover, the fact that SGs can be software-based allows them to offer customisable and personalised features tailored to each clinical case.

To promote the well-being and cognitive and motor development of children with ASD, it is essential to encourage the development of new SGs that explore the immersive benefits provided by these media. Furthermore, future research should rigorously assess the magnitude and durability of therapeutic gains offered by these interventions.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to investigate and describe the characteristics of SGs used for motor and cognitive development in young individuals with ASD. Based on the obtained results, it was possible to conclude that several studies with high methodological rigour address this context and suggest that SGs contribute significantly to these developmental domains compared to conventional therapeutic methods.

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